

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF USING GAME TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

Urokboeva Marjona Dadajon kizi

A first-year student of Foreign Languages Faculty

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

E-mail adress : marjonadadajonovna@gmail.com

Abstract : Nowadays, the demand for learning foreign languages is increasing. One of them is English. Different games can be used to learn English quickly and easily, using different innovative methods, technical tools, and interactive games that attract the attention of different students increases the student's interest in science. will be The article describes how to learn English quickly and easily with the help of various interesting games. These methods help students to be able to speak foreign languages perfectly and easily.

Key words : foreign language, method, student, interactive games, technical tools, style of role-playing games, Chainword game, Bingo.

ANNOTATSIYA: Hozirgi kunda chet tillarini o'rganishga bo'lgan talab kuchayib bormoqda. Shulardan biri ingliz tilidir. Ingliz tilini tez va oson o'rganish maqsadida turli hil o'yinlardan foydalansa bo'ladi, turli innovatsion metodlar, texnik vositalar, turli hil o'quvchilarni e'tiborini tortuvchi interfaol o'yinlardan foydalanish o'quvchining fanga bo'lgan qiziqishini ortishiga sabab bo'ladi. Maqolada ingliz tilini turli hil qiziqarli o'yinlar yordamida tez va oson o'rganish yoritib berilgan. Bu metodlar o'quvchilarning chet tillarini mukammal va shu tilda bemalol so'zlasha olishiga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tili, metod, o'quvchi, interfaol o'yinlar, texnik vositalar, Rolli o'yinlar uslubi, Chainword o'yini, Bingo.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В настоящее время растет спрос на изучение иностранных языков. Один из них английский. Для того, чтобы быстро и легко выучить английский язык, можно использовать различные игры, используя различные инновационные методы, технические средства, а интерактивные

игры, привлекающие внимание различных учащихся, повысят интерес школьника к науке. В статье рассказывается, как легко и быстро выучить английский язык с помощью различных интересных игр. Эти методы помогают учащимся в совершенстве и легко говорить на иностранных языках.

Ключевые слова: иностранный язык, метод, студент, интерактивные игры, технические средства, стиль ролевых игр, игра «Цепочка», Бинго.

INTRODUCTION

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, the game is considered as a situational exercise with the opportunity to repeat a speech pattern in conditions close to real situations. E.I. Passov in his book "A foreign language lesson at school" believes that: "the game is 1) activity; 2) motivation, lack of coercion; 3) individualized activity, deeply personal; 4) teaching in and through the team and education; 5) development of mental functions and abilities; 6) "learning with passion". The game is a strong incentive to learn a foreign language and an effective technique in the arsenal of a foreign language teacher, "a foreign language teacher is much more a universal tool that helps to turn the complex learning process into an interesting and favorite activity for students". Play is a powerful stimulus for language acquisition. The educational game cultivates a culture of communication and forms the ability to work in a team and in a team, and its skillful use in the lesson increases the desire and desire of students to play and communicate. [1] Games should be used to teach children not only English, but all foreign languages. If the lesson is taught using games, it will be easier for students to remember. It is advisable to start the lesson with grammar concepts, because this process can quickly make the students bored with the lessons, especially in the younger grades. As a result, his interest in the lesson fades. If the process of starting the lesson, i.e., greeting them, is conducted in a different non-traditional way, the enthusiasm of the students for the lesson will increase even more. If the lessons continue like this,

during the lesson their attention will be only on the lesson. They even look forward to English lessons. Various games can be used to make lessons more interesting.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

“**Role play**” is an effective means of forming the personality of students, their moral and willful qualities, the need to influence the world is realized in the game. This leads to serious changes in his psyche. The game is a huge bright window through which vital ideas and concepts about the surrounding world flow into the mental world of students. Play is the spark that ignites the spark of curiosity and curiosity.[4]

Chainword game (used in any class at the beginning level in learning any subject).

Purpose: to develop reading and spelling skills.

Find the words in this line. (can be used as a competition between teams).

Bingo game. (when repeating the topic "alphabet", "numbers" in any class).

Purpose: to develop listening skills.

Students fill in the space with letters/numbers. The teacher pronounces any letters / numbers in random order, the children listen and cut them in their field. The winner is the first to cross out all the letters/numbers and shout "bingo!"[1]

CONCLUSION

When using games, we can change them depending on the knowledge and age of the children, that is, make them easier or more complicated. The purpose of these above-mentioned games is to strengthen the memory of the students, to increase their mental capacity, quickness, intelligence, to remember new words easily and, most importantly, to organize the lesson in a meaningful way. Today, the educational process is mainly carried out in a traditional way, but at all stages of the educational system, continuous learning of foreign languages, as well as improving the

qualifications of teachers and teaching with modern educational and methodological materials provision requires further improvement. By introducing advanced methods of teaching with modern pedagogy and information-communication, it is desirable to make the growing young generation experts in the languages they are learning, and on the basis of this, they can speak these languages easily.

REFERENCES :

1. <https://valenteshop.ru/uz/vliyanie-igrovyyh-tehnologii-na-izuchenie-angliiskogo-primeneniye-igrovyyh/>
2. <https://mixcoin.ru/uz/strategy/vliyanie-syuzhetno-rolevyh-igr-na-razvitiye-doshkolnikov-vliyanie-syuzhetno-rolevoi/>
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/til-o-qitishda-o-yin-metodidan-foydalanish>